

Thoughts on strengthening the "3+2" Integrated School-running Cooperation between secondary and higher vocational Colleges

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Abstract: At present, there are many problems in vocational education in China, such as the lack of attraction of secondary vocational education, a serious shortage of students in higher vocational education, and poor connection between them. This paper starts from the problem of "3+2" integration of secondary and higher vocational colleges and puts forward the solution according to the actual situation of running a school.

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《Outline of The National Medium and Long term Plan for Education Reform and Development (2010-2020)》states that education will be basically modernized by 2020, and clearly identifies the coordinated development of secondary vocational education and higher vocational education as an important task in building a modern vocational education system. At present, there are still many problems in our vocational education.

I. Problems existing in the integrated reform of secondary and higher vocational colleges

Higher vocational colleges have their own policies, lack of overall planning and defects in comprehensive management. The teaching content is homogenized, and the

talent training program needs to be further coordinated.

The vocational teaching ability of teachers needs to be further improved. To a certain extent, there exists the phenomenon of unreasonable teacher structure in cooperative colleges, and the advantages of teachers among colleges have not realized the real supplementation.

II. The current secondary and higher vocational integration reform challenges

A series of new policies have brought new opportunities to our country's vocational education. Playing the important role of the "college entrance examination baton" can fundamentally reverse the unattractive situation of vocational education, so that students and parents eliminate anxiety, vocational education to be recognized by the society. But it also presents us with new challenges.

Our school is actively exploring the road of "3+2". Taking Business English major as the pilot, it has found a new way to strengthen the connection between secondary and higher vocational colleges.

III. Concrete measures to strengthen integration reform

(1) Higher vocational colleges shall participate in

secondary vocational enrollment and jointly formulate personnel training programs

The secondary and higher vocational schools jointly set the personnel training objectives, and build the curriculum system with the overall concept. The curriculum setting is from the shallow to the deep: the secondary vocational courses emphasize on the foundation and strong application, so that students can initially establish the vocational concept; Higher vocational courses focus on practice and innovation, and encourage students to give play to their subjective initiative and practicality in real or simulated work scenarios.

(2) Strengthen the management of class in secondary vocational schools, and try to preposition higher vocational courses

The important thing for secondary and higher vocational schools run schools jointly is whether the measures can be implemented. In secondary vocational schools and higher vocational schools, we have adopted the double head teacher system, which can not only strengthen the daily management of classes, but also let students have a preliminary understanding of various aspects of the higher vocational campus in advance. The head teacher of higher vocational colleges often attends team meetings to strengthen communication and exchange feelings with students, and introduce curriculum setting, campus culture, skills competition and other aspects of higher vocational college. Sometimes, by bringing class team activities to higher vocational campus, students can experience the campus atmosphere more directly and personally.

(3) Activate the connecting function of "Senior Three" and continuously improve students' vocational ability

In the previous "3+2" class, most of the students could directly enter higher vocational colleges to continue their

study, and there was no pressure to enter higher vocational colleges, so the students were likely to become slack. Especially in the last semester of the third grade, most students are in the state of "herding sheep". In general, the main reason for the "3+2" students' poor performance comes from the students' mediocre performance during this period. In response to this phenomenon, we have come up with a prescription: to strengthen the supervision of students by moving the examination tasks of certificate examination forward.

(4) Skill training and higher education should be carried out simultaneously to pave the way for students' growth

In terms of student management, secondary and higher vocational schools will present different management methods and characteristics due to the differences in students' age. If they are students of secondary vocational education, schools and teachers should pay more attention to the management and cultivation of their behavior habits. Therefore, higher vocational students are more willing to reflect the school's service, care and other humanistic aspects in their management. The school has been committed to the construction of talent training and successful overpass, guide, help and service students to choose their own growth path, in their own growth path harvest.

Vocational education needs to be rooted in the cultivation of skilled personnel, which requires a certain amount of time. "3+2" is not a one-way flow of "3" and "2", but a process of mutual penetration and joint promotion. It is believed that "3+2" education can be integrated and connected as long as secondary vocational colleges and vocational colleges can cooperate with each other to explore and find their own paths to success.

References:

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